

Proposed Model Factors Affecting on Agriculture Import and Export Performance

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Abstract:

Import and export is an extremely important activity for each country and import-export businesses. Import and export activities play an important role in the national economy. So how to improve the efficiency of import and export activities? The article has reviewed previous studies and analyzed to propose a research model of factors affecting the efficiency of agricultural product import and export of Vietnamese enterprises.

Keywords: *Import and export performance, Vietnam*

1. Introduction

With the current era of economic integration, in order to survive and develop, each country cannot withdraw, but needs to open its doors to trade with many countries around the world. Before that change, the import-export industry has been holding a very important role in the economy. So how are the roles of the import-export industry being shown?

Import and export trade is the exchange of goods and services between countries through the act of buying and selling. Such exchange is a form of social relations and reflects the economic interdependence between nations' separate producers of goods. We cannot deny the great role that the import-export profession brings to the economy today.

The first is the growth of the economy in terms of quantity. Thanks to the import-export industry, Vietnam's economy always maintains a high GDP growth rate. Compared to the period before import and export was born and developed, that is a huge difference thanks to which Vietnam's economy has increased many levels and is comparable to many countries in the world.

Through import and export activities, it is possible to increase foreign currency earnings, improve the balance of payments, increase revenue for the state budget, stimulate technological innovation, gain access to new business forms, and create new business opportunities. more jobs for a large number of people of working age who have high qualifications, creating competition between domestic and imported goods, improving people's living standards.

Thanks to import and export activities, we can combine the country's own resources, potentials such as natural resources, labor, and shortages such as capital and technology to open the economy to take advantage of capital. aid, inheriting scientific and technical achievements combined with the potential to create strong growth for the economy, contributing to shortening the economic gap of our country with developed countries in the world.

At the enterprise level: Through export activities, enterprises achieve their basic goal which is profit, a goal that every business must aim for. Profit is the first goal as well as the most important goal of the business, it decides and governs other activities such as: research, search for new markets; purchasing and creating sources of goods; conducting reserve activities, services ... domestic enterprises have the opportunity to participate and access to the world market. If successful, this will be the basis for businesses to expand their markets and production capabilities. Export helps businesses improve their competitiveness: Due to the competitive pressure of domestic and foreign enterprises to stand firm, enterprises have to renew equipment and retrain staff. employees to improve competitiveness. When participating in international business, it will inevitably put

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businesses in a fiercely competitive environment where, if they want to survive and develop, businesses must constantly improve quality, improve models, code, reduce product cost. This will be a factor promoting the production and business activities of enterprises. The combination of export and import in the context of a multi-component commodity economy will contribute to promoting joint ventures between domestic and foreign enterprises voluntarily, expanding business relations, exploiting and exporting goods. Effectively use existing resources, create jobs for workers, it increases their income and also promotes the creativity of workers. Export leads to cooperation between scientists and businesses in a practical way from the manufacturer's side, it opens up the source of gray matter at home and abroad.

So how to improve the efficiency of import and export, that is a question many researchers as well as practice want to be answered. However, there are very few studies on this subject. This paper builds a model to evaluate the factors affecting the import-export efficiency of Vietnamese agricultural enterprises.

2. Research overview

2.1. Resource management and export performance

In the export literature, the role of managerial resources in improving the export performance of firms is well recognized (Sousa et al., 2008). Unlike large enterprises, the international activities of small and medium enterprises are significantly influenced by the knowledge and attitudes of managers towards exports (Miesenbock, 1988). This is consistent with a gradual approach (Johanson & Vahlne, 1977), where the manager's perceived spiritual distance (often influenced by knowledge and attitudes) plays an important role in shaping the internationalization process of the company.

Many previous studies have recognized the lack of export knowledge as one of the main obstacles hindering the operation of companies in foreign markets (Altıntaş, Tokol, & Harcar, 2007; Pinho & Martins, 2010; Suarez-Ortega, 2003). In an often uncertain and uncertain foreign market, possessing relevant knowledge about exports will assist business managers in their decision-making process (Seringhaus, 1987). It also allows them to respond more effectively to export obstacles (Nalcaci & Yagci, 2014; Nemkova, Souchon, & Hughes, 2012). According to Simi, language ability was found to have a positive effect on exports (Leonidou, Katsikeas, & Piercy, 1998; Stoian, Rialp, & Rialp, 2011). Such a skill would allow managers to establish useful contacts and avoid communication problems (Leonidou et al., 1998; Nemkova et al., 2012). Perception and favorable attitude towards exports is another prerequisite for the export activities of SMEs (Naidu & Prasad, 1994; Zou & Stan, 1998). Positive perceptions increase human commitment and resource allocation to export activities, thereby improving performance (Papadopoulos & Martin, 2010). Similarly, when experienced managers appreciate and understand the value of exporting, a company is more likely to become a regular exporter (Naidu & Prasad, 1994).

2.2. Technology resources and export performance

Technological resources in the form of innovative and unique technology (E. D. Wagner & McCombs, 1995) and/or proprietary patents (Moini, 1995) can constitute an international competitive advantage. There is a lot of mixed evidence about their effect on export performance reported in the literature (Lefebvre, Lefebvre, & Bourgault, 1998). In fact, while technology resources have been reported to contribute positively (Piercy, Kaleka, & Katsikeas, 1998), in the short term, technology acquisition can generate sunk costs (Mattoussi & Ayadi, 2016), which will negatively affect performance (Knight, 2001). Especially for developing countries like Vietnam, where low costs are often a competitive advantage, technology can negatively affect international operations (Zhao & Zou, 2002). Similarly, Alvarez (2007) has shown that, for reasons related to costs, technological factors do not seem to be an important prerequisite for firms' export frequency.

2.3. Innovation and export performance

Developing new products and processes can offer companies a number of benefits, including improved productivity and increased efficiency. In the international context, several studies have reported the positive contribution of innovation (measured through research and development [R&D] spending) to improving export

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performance (Díez Vial & Fernández- Olmos, 2013; Robson & Freel, 2008; Singh, 2009; Zahra, Ireland, & Hitt, 2000). However, several studies conducted in developing countries have yielded contrasting findings. While evidence from Malaysia cannot prove a significant link between the two (Man, 2010), a study from Ghana and Bosnia Herzegovina suggests that innovation is important for exports only when The company operates in a highly competitive environment and when customer requirements are higher than dynamic (Boso, Story, Cado Gan, Micevski, & Kadic-Maglajlic, 2013). Similarly, a Chinese study reported that innovation only increases the survival of exporters when these jobs are highly profitable (Deng et al., 2014). Especially for SMEs operating in developing countries, the high sunk costs associated with innovation activities can easily outweigh the benefits arising from such activities, a phenomenon well known. called “responsibility for innovation” (Deng et al., 2014).

2.4. Marketability and export performance

Based on RBV, marketability as marketing mix processes can be rare, valuable, irreplaceable, and inimitable sources of international competitive advantage that can lead to operational efficiencies. superior performance of the company (Morgan, Katsikeas, & Vorhies, 2012; Vorhies & Morgan, 2005). In the export literature, it is widely agreed that possessing special marketing capabilities will greatly enhance export performance in a variety of ways. The ability to market in general can be a source of brand advantage and low cost will give a company a competitive advantage over its competitors (Zou, Fang, & Zhao, 2003). Competitive capabilities in the form of information capabilities (Ibeh & Young, 2001; Kaleka, 2012), pricing capabilities (Obadia & Stöttinger, 2014), advertising (Díez-Vial & Fernández-Olmos, 2013; Styles & Ambler, 1994), and the ability to advertise (Serra, Pointon, & Abdou, 2012) were both found to have a positive effect on export performance. Tailoring marketing strategies to the requirements of foreign markets allows companies to satisfy customer requirements in export markets (Azar & Drogendijk, 2014). Finally, operational planning as part of the marketing strategy was also revealed to be an important prerequisite for export operations. Planning often prompts the company to conduct market research and allocate necessary resources to tailor their product/service, which can lead to increased export performance (Knight, 2001). . Therefore, it can also be argued that meeting the requirements of foreign customers, allocating sufficient resources to export, and adapting to changes in prices will also result in the company exporting frequently.

2.5. Relationship resources (relationship quality) and export activities

Network-based view The export behavior literature has shown that the financial difficulties faced by firms affect their probability of initiating exports (Bellone, Nesta, & Schiavo, 2010).). One of the reasons why access to finance is so important is the sunk costs associated with investments in product customization, marketing, distribution, and logistics (Roberts & Tybout, 1997). . In the context that SMEs often have limited financial resources, and especially in an emerging economy characterized by significant credit constraints, such as Vietnam, cooperative activities constitute a solution. attractive alternative for SMEs to access external resources. Collaborative confirmation is a common practice among businesses. Such companies use both formal and informal relationships (Coviello & Munro, 1997) with other stakeholders such as customers, distributors, and competitors to access non-resources. available. Called the “network perspective,” this approach argues that firms' strategic decisions are influenced by external relationships. In the international context, the network perspective has also been widely adopted. Johanson and Mattsson (1988) argue that as a company nationalizes, its relationships with other network members become more important and of greater value. Such relationships often assist companies in accessing additional resources and markets to enhance their internationalization. Assets obtained through the company's external relationships are called "relational resources". Lavie (2006) defines relational resources as the set of resources that can emerge from SME relationships and connections with peer companies and business partners. In this study, they are divided into local relations resources and foreign relations resources. While the former relates to resources obtained through relationships with peer companies operating in the country, the latter reflects resources obtained through relationships with foreign

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buyers (importers). password). These resources can take the form of market knowledge, skills, expertise, and equipment.

Resources for local relations.

While most previous research regarding the role of networks in internationalization has tended to focus on international networks, domestic networks can also play an active role in supporting support for international zoning by SMEs (Manolova, Manev, & Gyoshev, 2010). This may be especially relevant for SMEs from emerging economies (Nowinski & Rialp, 2013). The cooperative activities of SMEs with development outsiders in the local market are generally a valuable source of external assets (I. F. Wilkinson, Mattsson, & Easton, 2000). These networks act as an additional resource for the internal resources of small and medium enterprises. They help to reduce uncertainty and uncertainty in export markets through control. Therefore, researchers have argued that companies should be seen as part of a network through which a pool of resources is accessible (Wright, Westhead, & Ucbasaran, 2007).

In the international context, it is generally agreed that companies that are part of industrial networks and business groups benefit from the exchange of foreign knowledge, which increases their export performance (Felzensztein, Ciravegna, Robson, & Amorós, 2015; Freeman, Styles, & Lawley, 2012; He & Wei, 2013; Singh, 2009). As Manolova et al. (2010) argues, inter-organizational cooperation with other domestic firms, especially if established in the early stages of their operations, aids their internationalization. Likewise, being part of an intranet increases a company's visibility and reach to international markets and overseas customers (Boehe, 2013). Close cooperation with local suppliers improves the quality of inputs, which in turn improves product quality and increases international competitiveness (I. F. Wilkinson et al., 2000). In Africa, relational resources acquired through formal and informal relationships constitute an important support for the internationalization of firms (Ibeh et al., 2012). With regard to philanthropy, previous evidence suggests that the concentration of exporting firms has a positive and significant effect on the likelihood of becoming a long-term exporter (Alvarez, 2007).

Resources for foreign relations

Relational resources acquired through corporate connections and cooperation with their foreign partners (importers) are important determinants of export performance (Fafchamps et al. , 2008; Haddoud, Jones, & Newbery, 2017; Kim & Hemmert, 2016; Lages, Lages, & Lages, 2005; Leonidou, Samiee, Aykol, & Talias, 2014; Ling-Yee, 2004; Ural, 2009). Evidence from the UK shows that compared to local networks, foreign relationships have a greater influence on firms' exports (Haddoud et al., 2017). Foreign network works are particularly useful in generating knowledge about foreign markets and enhancing exports (Ling-Yee, 2004). Uncertainties related to export markets are likely to subside as exporters and importers exchange strategic information about foreign markets (Ural, 2009). Close cooperation with importers can be seen as a source of cross-cultural intelligence and knowledge that provides exporters with a competitive advantage (Kim & Hemmert, 2016). It can also create a team spirit, helping exporters overcome international challenges and obstacles, reduce costs and improve performance (Leonidou et al., 2014). ; Zain & Ng, 2006). In particular, through foreign relationships, companies can benefit from established distribution channels (Coviello & Munro, 1997), gaining access to additional potential buyers (Björkman & Kock). , 1995), and opportunities to build credibility and trust in foreign markets (Chetty & Patterson, 2002; Zain & Ng, 2006). This phenomenon is of particular relevance to African countries, where colonial bonds often affect the export destinations of companies. Evidence from Morocco shows that international networks (with former colonies) increase exports to Mance (Fafchamps et al., 2008). Similarly, evidence from Uganda (Bakunda, 2004), Nigeria (Ibeh, 2001) and Ethiopia (Belwal & Chala, 2008) suggests that foreign cooperation plays an important role in the internationalization of firms. . Furthermore, international networks can also boost exports. Consistent with Uppsala's view of internationalization (Johanson & Vahlne, 1977), previous evidence has emphasized that unlike new exporters, who often require objective knowledge to get started, Regular and experienced exporters need experiential knowledge to maintain their operations abroad (Crick, 1995). This type of foreign know-how can be obtained through regular cooperation with foreign countries. Similarly, Uppsala's view is revised that

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cooperation and commitment with strong partners is likely to lead to building and learning, to trust, which in turn leads to the identification of foreign opportunities new and thus maintain international business (Johanson & Vahlne, 2009).

3. RESEARCH MODEL

Figure 1. Research model

Based on the literature review, a complete list of potential sources cited in the export literature as export determinants for each form was developed. As mentioned earlier, the present study considers both resources and capabilities and follows the RBV smarting process, including both concepts under enterprise resource scope. The study collected the most cited sources reported in the export literature. Then, based on previous studies that applied a similar approach to resource concept formation (Beleska-Spasova et al., 2012; Leonidou et al., 2011), the study listed an open list of resources. Broaden resource factors down to 12 resources grouped into five categories: technology resources, innovation capabilities, management resources, marketability capabilities, and relational resources.

Import and export performance

Because Vietnamese firms are reluctant to disclose financial data (T. Wilkinson & Brouters, 2006), the study used a perception-based measure called the composite measure “EXPERF” developed by Zou, Taylor and Oslo (1998). The index combines both objective and subjective measures and includes three performance icons: financial, strategic, and satisfaction measures, each of which is rated on a five-word scale that is “fully congruent.” agree” to “strongly disagree” (Beleska-Spasova et al., 2012)

Supply chain efficiency

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Global supply chain efficiency is a prerequisite for export efficiency (Le Trung Thanh et al., 2019). Therefore, the author studies the impact of the above factors on the efficiency of supply chain management and thereby affects the import and export efficiency of enterprises.

3. Conclusion

Industrialization of the country following appropriate steps is an inevitable way to overcome our country's poverty and underdevelopment. In order to carry out the industrialization and modernization of the country, we must first import a large number of modern machinery and equipment from outside to equip the production. Capital for import is usually based on the main sources: borrowing, aid, foreign investment and export. Borrowed capital must be repaid, while aid and foreign investment are limited, these sources are often dependent on foreign countries. Therefore, the most important source of capital for imports is exports. In fact, which country can increase exports, imports will increase accordingly. Conversely, if imports are larger than exports, the trade balance deficit will be too large, which may adversely affect the national economy.

In the future, external capital will increase, but all investment and borrowing opportunities from foreign countries and international organizations will only be available when investors and lenders see the ability to export - capital. single loan to repay the debt into reality.

+ Export contributes to economic restructuring and promotes production development:

The structure of production and consumption in the world has changed dramatically. It is the result of the modern scientific and technological revolution, the economic restructuring in the process of industrialization in line with the development trend of the world economy is inevitable for our country.

Today, most countries take the needs of the world market to organize production. That has a positive impact on the economic restructuring, promoting economic production and development. This effect is shown:

- Export creates favorable conditions for other industries to develop. For example, when developing exports, there will be sufficient opportunities for the development of the production of raw materials such as cotton, jute, etc. The development of the food processing industry (rice, coffee, etc.) may lead to the equipment manufacturing industries serving it.

- Export creates the possibility to expand the consumption market, create conditions for production to develop and stabilize.

Exporting facilitates the expansion of input supply for production, improving domestic production capacity.

+ Export plays an active role in renewing production equipment and technology.

Export activities are business activities in the world market, a market where competition is increasingly fierce. The existence and development of export goods depends greatly on the quality and price; therefore depends greatly on the technology of their production. This motivates domestic manufacturing enterprises to always innovate and improve equipment and machinery to improve production quality. On the other hand, exporting in a fiercely competitive market economy also requires businesses to improve the skills and qualifications of workers.

+ Exports have a positive impact on creating jobs and improving people's lives.

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The impact of exports on livelihoods includes many aspects. First of all, through export activities, with many different stages, millions of workers have been attracted to work and have relatively high incomes, increasing the value of working days and increasing the national income.

Exports also create capital to import essential consumer goods, serve the people's lives and meet the consumption needs of the people, and improve the material and spiritual life of workers.

+ Export is the basis for expanding and promoting our country's external economic relations:

Promoting exports plays a role in enhancing international cooperation with other countries, enhancing our country's position and role in the international arena..., export and export manufacturing industry promote credit funds, investment, expansion of international transport On the other hand, it is the external economic relations that we mentioned above that create the premise for the expansion of exports.

It can be said that exports not only play the role of a catalyst to support economic development, but also together with import activities as an internal factor that directly participates in solving problems within the economy. economic factors such as capital, labor, technology, consumption sources, markets, etc. For our country, a strong export orientation is one of the important goals in external economic development, considered a matter of strategic significance for economic development and industrialization of the country. through which can take advantage of opportunities, apply modern science and technology, shorten the difference in development level of Vietnam compared to the world. Experience shows that any country and in any period promoting exports, its economy during this time has a high growth rate.

References

- i Duong Chieu Bang, 2009. *Some solutions to improve the quality of export goods in the Mekong Delta. Master thesis in economics. Major in Business Administration, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh.*
- ii Duong Huu Hanh, 2005. *Export Marketing Strategies and Plans. Statistical publisher.*
- iii Dang Minh Phung, 2009. *Development Strategy of Long An Food Company to 2015. Master's Thesis in Economics. Major in Business Administration, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh.*
- iv Doan Thi Hong Van and Kim Ngoc Dat, 2011. *Import-Export Management. General Publisher.*
- v Nguyen Quoc Thai, 2011. *Solutions to promote export of Vietnamese goods to West Africa market. Master thesis in economics. Major in Commerce, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh.*
- vi Nguyen Thi Thuong (2013), "Enhancing the attraction of Japanese FDI into Vietnam", *Economic and Forecasting Journal*, No. 23, pp. 39-41.
- vii Nguyen Thi Thuong, Nguyen Duy Tuan (2014), "The relationship between FDI and domestic investment: A view from quantitative analysis", *Journal of Economics and Forecasting, special issue March 2014*, p. 9- 11.
- viii Nguyen Thi Thuong (2014), "The role of group interests in public policy making", *Proceedings of the Workshop "Group interests and interest groups in the market mechanism: a study of experiences in developed countries". development*", pp. 28-30.
- ix Nguyen Thi Thuong (2016), "Factors affecting the ability to attract FDI in the context of international economic integration: An analysis of the Vietnamese case", *Journal of Economics and Development*, No. 223 (II), pp. 68-75.

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- x *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2016), "Attracting Japanese FDI into Hanoi through investment promotion activities", Proceedings of the National Conference "Relation between remittances and investment activities", pp. 401- 413.*
- xi *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2017), "Evaluating the impact of FDI on Vietnam's imports", Journal of Economics and Forecasting, No. 36, pp. 3-7.*
- xii *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2017), Head of Project "The relation between foreign direct investment and export at Vietnam", Project at grassroots level, Code: KTQD/E2016.14, Chairman.*
- xiii *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2018), "Factors affecting overseas investment: A case study of Viettel", Economic and Forecasting Journal, October 30, 2018, pp. 108-111.*
- xiv *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2018), "Vietnam's agricultural exports stand in front of international economic integration", Journal of Information and Communication, No. 345, pp. 22-26.*
- xv *Nguyen Thi Thuong (2019), "Vietnamese employment and income of workers in FDI enterprises in Vietnam", Proceedings of the National Scientific Conference "The current state of development of the FDI sector in the implementation of the Sustainable Development Strategy sustainable in Vietnam", pp. 192-201.*
- xvi *Nguyen Thi Lien Diep and Pham Van Nam, 2010. Business strategy and policy. Labor and Social Publishing House.*
- xvii *Porter, E. M, 1998. National Competitive Advantage. Translate from English. Translator Nguyen Ngoc Toan et al., 2008. Youth Publishing House.*
- xviii *Ton That Nguyen Thiem, 2005. Market, Strategy, Structure: Competition for added value, positioning and business development. Ho Chi Minh City General Publishing House.*
- xix *Tran Hoa Phuong, 2013. Vietnam's agricultural export advantages after joining WTO. National Political Publishing House.*
- xx *Tran Phuoc Thuan, 2009. Some solutions to promote the marketing of goods of Can Tho Agricultural Products and Food Export Company. Master thesis in economics. Major in Commerce, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh.*
- xxi *Truong Van Cuong, 2009. Solutions to promote Vietnam's export of goods until 2017. Master's thesis in economics. Major in Business Administration, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh.*
- xxii *Vo Hung Dung, 2012. Vietnam's commodity rice exports from 1989 to 2011. Can Tho University Publishing House.*